

Impact of the Graphene Synthesis on Electrochemical Properties of Graphene — Graphite Systems

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The electrochemical impedance spectroscopy and scanning electron microscopy investigated the relationship between the electrical parameters of the graphite-graphene systems with various graphite content and the structural-morphological features of graphene. The dependence between graphite-graphene ratio and electrochemical properties was found. The impact of graphite content and media of synthesis on changing the conductivity type was determined. The changing of the graphite concentration in the graphene/graphite mixture regulates the type of doping and electrical parameters of the mixture. The impact of heat treatment on the change of electrical parameters of the whole system is shown.

Introduction

Graphene-based supercapacitors are one of the most discussed topics in the scientific community today due to the ability of graphene to build such structures as graphene sheets rolled into a tube with a diameter in the range of 1 nm ÷ 100 nm (1). The mixture of the graphene materials (nanotubes and sheets) can perform a high capacitance (290 F/g and 200 F/g), in aqueous and organic electrolytes (2). These values were 20% higher than for pure graphene-based electrodes. This was explained by the fact that graphene alone can repackage with the formation of graphite and nanotubes due to Van der Waals, reducing the active surface area. A composite of these structures, on the contrary, prevents repackaging ability and the formation of beams in the entire graphene structure, thereby increasing the active surface area, which accelerates the diffusion of ions (3). The nitrogen-doped graphene/graphite mixture provides excellent electrochemical characteristics for the lithium-ion battery, such as a high specific capacity of up to 781 mAh/g, a bandwidth of 351 mAh/g, and instead stability - maintaining a capacity of 98.1% at 10 °C after a cycle of 1000 cycles (4). Therefore, our study aimed to establish the effects of graphene content and kind of synthesis on the structural changes and electrical parameters (conductivity and capacity) of graphite- graphene mixture.

Components of mixture were electrolytic graphite and graphenes. Graphenes were synthesized using two methods of plasma arc discharge from an aqueous and nitrogen medium (water and liquid nitrogen). Graphenes and graphite mixed in the mass ratio according to the table 1. The heat treatment of samples carried out during one hour with a gradual increase in temperature up to 250 °C.

TABLE I. Synthesis method, composition, and heat treatment conditions of graphite-graphene mixtures

Number of samples and synthesis method	Mass ratio graphene/ graphite	Heating temperature °C
1. The liquid nitrogen media	1/5	25
2. The liquid nitrogen media	1/3	25
3. The liquid nitrogen media	1/1	25
4. The liquid nitrogen media	1/1	250
5. The water media	1/1	25
6. The water media	1/3	25
7. The water media	1/3	250

The capacity values and the active resistance of the samples fixed the differences in these systems. The mixture with graphene from water media reduces the average values of capacity relatively to graphene from nitrogen media by 10 times, and significantly increases the active resistance at the mass ratio of graphene to graphite 1:3, and with a ratio of 1:1, they are commensurate. Such differences are based on various structural and morphological properties of samples (fig.1).

Figure 1 The SEM images of the graphene synthesized from liquid nitrogen media -1, and from water media -2.

Calculations of the average electrical conductivity data in systems with graphene synthesized in a nitrogen medium show the dependence of the increase of the electrical conductivity and an increase of the capacitance on the graphene content (fig. 2). High values of capacitance and conductivity were obtained in systems with a ratio of graphene/graphite 1: 1 (sample 3, 4). However, the maximum average values of capacity (into 2 times higher) are observed in a system with equal content of graphene and graphite, which is synthesized in nitrogen with heat treatment of the sample at 250 oC . By graphical integration of the active resistance and capacity data on the frequency plane (5, 6) was fixed the changes in the charges distribution in the samples in various frequency ranges. So, the media affect the ability of graphene to be in an open sheet stay, and regulate future interactions between graphene and graphite. Graphite regulates the main electrochemical properties of the mixture in the case of the graphene from nitrogen media. The change of the graphite concentration in the graphene/graphite mixture may regulate the type of doping and electrical parameters of the whole mixture.

Figure 2. The scheme of changing electrochemical properties (capacitance, conductivity, and surface charge distribution) in the graphene from liquid nitrogen media according to electrochemical impedance data and Raman spectra.

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References

1. Q. Cheng, J. Tang, J. Ma, H. Zhang, N. Shinya, L.C. Qin, *Physical Chemistry Chemical Physics*, **39**(13), 17615 (2011).
2. A. Ansaldo, P. Bondavalli, S. Bellani, A. E. Del Rio Castillo, M. Prato., V. Pellegrini, F. Bonaccorso, *ChemNanoMat.*, **6**(3), 436 (2017).
3. W. Guanghui, L. Ruiyi, L. Zaijun, L. Junkang, G. Zhiguo, W. Guangli, *Electrochimica Acta.*, **171**, 156 (2015).
4. M. Terrones, A.R. Botello-Méndez, J. Campos-Delgado, F. López-Urías, Y.I. Vega-Cantú, F.J. Rodríguez-Macías, H. Terrones, *Nano today*, **4**(5), 351 (2010).
5. O.L. Riabokin, A.V. Boichuk, K.D. Pershina, *Surf. Engin. Appl. Electrochem.*, **54**(6), 614 (2018).
6. O. Boichuk, K. Pershina, O. Riabokin, A. Kravchenko, R. Panteleimonov, *Ukrainian Chemistry Journal*, **86** (4), 108 (2020).